

M3.1 Implementation plan mid-scale pilot

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1. Introduction

The Horizon Europe funded QUANTUM project aims at providing guidance on a quality and utility label, out of the testing of a data quality, utility and maturity labelling mechanism in a substantive number of data holders. Ideally, this labelling mechanism could be adopted in HealthData@EU as foreseen in the European Health Data Space (EHDS) regulation (article 78) for secondary use. The project has been kicked off in the beginning of 2024 and is focusing on the following objectives:

1. Conceptualise and develop a data quality and utility label in the context of a data holder maturity model (WP1);
2. Design, develop and test the labelling of the data sets' quality and utility, and data holders' maturity (WP2/WP3);
3. Analyse the implementation challenges with a view to enabling the transferability and sustainability of the labelling mechanism as part of HealthData@EU (WP4);
4. Develop a capacity building and outreach program that allows a broad engagement of the data quality professional community (WP5).

This milestone report, pertaining to WP3, provides the implementation plan for the so-called mid-scale test of the quality & utility labels being proposed (WP1) and implemented (WP2) within QUANTUM. The mid-scale test will be run between April 2025 and December 2025.

1.1. Quality & utility label

1.1.1. Fundamental concepts

When developing generic quality and utility labels for health datasets it is crucial to develop a common understanding of the fundamental concepts of quality and utility. In the QUANTUM approach:

Quality refers to features that describe the content of a dataset, typically completeness, uniqueness, accuracy, validity, timeliness, and consistency of the data.

Fit-for-use is equivalent to a dataset's "potential" utility, typically information that describes the dataset in a standard manner, such as source, provenance or lineage, content, distribution, etc. Fit-for-use talks about the "potential" utility of a dataset, while the actual utility can only be informed by the user experience –in QUANTUM, the actual utility is referred to as fit-for-purpose.

Fit-for-purpose refers to the actual utility of an accessed dataset according to the objective of the health data request. The information necessary to evaluate fit-for-purpose depends on the user's experience. This information needs to be added to the description of a dataset as fit-for-purpose metadata.

Maturity is a feature at the data holder level. It refers to the level of automation of data and data quality management procedures.

1.1.2. Proposed quality & utility label

Deliverable D1.1 “Specification of the data sets’ quality and utility label”¹ provides an overview of the quality and utility label proposed by QUANTUM to be tested in the mid-scale pilot organised by WP3. The proposed label was based on desk research on data quality and utility dimensions, expert consultations and on a formal consensus process using Delphi methodology, followed by the final selection and refinement of a relevant and consensual set of criteria for assessing the quality and usefulness of datasets.

The initial comprehensive literature review and expert consultations identified 54 data quality and utility dimensions. Through iterative rounds (Delphi consensus process and an expert nominal group) and statistical validation, the list was refined arriving at 12 data quality and utility dimensions (e.g. accuracy, completeness, etc.), generic to any data reuse purpose and any type of data. It may be worthwhile noting that the utility dimension of the label in particular focuses on the fit-for use aspects of the dataset while the actual fit-for-purpose heavily depends on the actual reuse scenario and can therefore only be determinant by the user (see above for the definition of fit-for-use vs fit-for-purpose).

Subsequently, for each dimension, quantifiable metrics and scoring criteria were developed, ensuring agreement between experts from different data quality domains. For some of the dimensions, two metrics were defined, resulting ultimately in 15 metrics, each with their objective scoring criteria. These were subsequently implemented in the tool developed in WP2 (see below).

1.2. Tool developed and small-scale test results

The specifications for the data quality & utility label that has been delivered by WP1 constitutes the basis for the tool developed by WP2. It allows to systematically register the quality & utility labels for any health datasets, visualise those in a user-friendly manner and subsequently export the resulting labels in a publishable format (PDF) as well as a format (RDF) compatible with most data catalogue tools.

1.2.1. The QUANTUM data quality labeling tool

The QUANTUM Data Quality and Maturity Labelling Tool is a web-based application designed to:

- Evaluate data quality and utility through self-assessment: Enable data holders to input metadata about their datasets, facilitating the calculation of data quality according to the metrics and dimensions defined by QUANTUM partners².
- Evaluate organizational maturity: Assess the maturity level on data quality management of an organization or entity based on a maturity matrix developed by the QUANTUM

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14795197>

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14795197>

consortium (see QUANTUM D1.2 for further details)³.

The tool is structured into two main dashboards:

1. **Data Quality Dashboard:** This dashboard allows users to self-assess the QUANTUM data quality and utility dimensions of a dataset within a user's catalogue (Figure 1). This information is then used to generate the QUANTUM data quality and utility label. Users can view the details of the computed label and its score, and download the assessment as an RDF file in .ttl format to be landed in the Health DCAT-AP specification and DQV vocabularies for interoperability with HealthData@EU standards.

Fig 1: Two screenshots of the QUANTUM labeling tool: on the left part of the data quality and utility assessment page is shown where the metrics for the data quality label are entered and on the right the data quality certificate (“quality label”) generated by the assessment showing the attained score for each quality and utility dimension.

2. **Maturity Dashboard:** This dashboard provides an overview of the organization's maturity score. Users can review and update their maturity matrix values as needed, maintaining an accurate and up-to-date maturity profile.

Additionally, in order to ease the task of organizing the data-holder's information, the QUANTUM labeling tool includes the functionality of managing the catalogues and datasets. This capacity of organizing catalogues and datasets is independent of the quality assessment and the generation of the quality label, so the user can assess and generate labels for all their datasets or only some

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14795415>

of them.

It is still under discussion how all the metadata related with quality, utility and maturity will be stored and linked with the QUANTUM label in the HealthDCAT-AP catalogue.

Fig 2: Screenshot of the QUANTUM maturity dashboard, showing the results of the maturity assessment for an organization.

The QUANTUM tool is available both as a web version and a downloadable packaged tool to be deployed within the local environment of participants in the test.⁴

1.2.2. Main conclusions from small-scale test

WP2 executed a first round of user testing for the quality labeling tool, the so-called small-scale test. Test participants could use the web version of the tool to enter the QUANTUM quality labels for a dataset of choice to score the tool on various aspects, including its usability. The participants were asked to provide their feedback in an online survey. The overall results of this test were encouraging, although many suggestions for improvements as well as clear software bugs were reported.

Subsequently an online workshop with pilot users was organised which offered the opportunity for discussion between testers and tool developers resulting in an additional set of detailed evaluation results and improvement suggestions.

A number of overarching recommendations were articulated as the main outcomes of the small-scale test:

1. Guidance is needed to identify the right persons to conduct the tool evaluations. This includes clarifying the required previous knowledge by the person and defining the role or function within the organization or unit that is best suited for these tasks.

⁴ <https://quantumpilot.upv.es/> and https://github.com/quantum-label/quantum_labelling_tool

2. The platform should be made more self-explanatory. This means providing clearer instructions on how to use it, including definitions, examples, and use cases. This also entails improving the process of extracting and preparing data from datasets or their organizations, as this is a crucial step before introducing key information into the platform to obtain the Data Quality labeling and the maturity assessment. It is important to clarify which is the focus of the maturity assessment: at organization or unit level.
3. Improving the visualization and interpretability of outcomes is essential. This includes providing more feedback to users, enhancing graphical representations and the attractiveness of the platform, which at the end supports the intention of use and adoptability of the system. It was also concluded that it is necessary to review the RDF generation process to add more detailed information, and to provide additional formats for downloading the labelling, such as a pdf file. This has been accommodated in the meantime.

It is recommended to address these recommendations before the mid-scale pilot, as described in the present implementation plan, is started.

2. High-level objectives of WP3

The high-level objectives of QUANTUM WP3 (Mid-scale implementation of the label) are:

1. Deploy the quality & utility label tool developed in WP2 in a larger group of data holders participating in the project (“mid-scale test”);
2. Feed the learnings from the mid-scale test into WP2 to further enhance the tool;
3. Assess all aspects of the tool implementation process where data holders will provide insights for transferability and sustainability;
4. Translate the outcomes of the mid-scale test into guidance for the eventual delegated and implementing acts derived from the application of the legislative proposal for the HealthData@EU.

The activities of WP3 are divided over 4 tasks:

- **3.1 - Implementation plan** (Nov 2024 - Mar 2025). Preparations for the mid-scale test through a series of interviews with representative data holders informing the ultimate implementation plan as outlined in the present milestone report.
- **3.2 - Mid-scale implementation pilot** (Apr 2025 – Dec 2025). The execution of the mid-scale test: approaching data holders to participate in the test, provide support to the test participants through a help desk, collect the test results, and interact with WP2 to incorporate the enhancements suggested by the testers in the new version of the tool.
- **3.3 - Implementation assessment** (Sep 2025 – Dec 2025). Overall assessment of the test user experiences will translate into a deliverable report to provide insights into aspects like feasibility, barriers, facilitators, institutional preparedness and governance, etc., informing future transferability and sustainability (T3.4). It will also serve as feedback to improve the tool (WP2) and future versions of the quality, utility and maturity specification (WP1).
- **3.4 - Transfer and sustainability** (Jan 2026 – Feb 2026). Translation of the outcomes of the mid-scale pilot to the real-life situation under HealthData@EU. Two workshops will be

organized to define these conclusions and translate these into further recommendations to be incorporated in future delegated and implementing acts under the EHDS.

Fig 3: Gantt Chart showing the sequence and dependency of tasks within WP3 as well as between WP2 and WP3. It is foreseen that the first round of mid-scale testing feeds into task 2.4 for consideration in a labeling tool upgrade. The resulting enhanced tool will be subjected to further testing in task 3.2.

The effective execution of the WP3 tasks requires close interaction with WP2 as shown in Fig 3. We have scheduled at least two rounds of testing for the mid-scale test with an intermediate upgrade/update of the tool by WP2, though this update of the tool will be done in an agile continuous delivery manner along the pilot. We expect that on top of this a third, smaller round of testing will be needed to address certain gaps in the test (in terms of type of data holders or in terms of actual testing) that will only be identified during the testing. The mid-scale test itself is scheduled to run for 9 months, with a kick-off meeting in April 2025 and then running for the rest of the year.

3. In-depth interviews with future test participants

A series of in-depth interviews have been executed with anticipated implementers/users of the QUANTUM tool to establish quality labels for datasets. The interviews were held in advance of the planned implementation and testing of the tool in the mid-scale pilot. All interviewees were data holders as defined in the EHDS.

The in-depth interviews were aiming to get an overview of:

- the institutional preparedness for the implementation of the QUANTUM labeling tool
- potential barriers in using the tool
- risk analysis and contingency plan for the deployment of the tool
- participants' expectations with respect to the testing and the QUANTUM labeling tool

The results of this interview have informed the preparation of the present implementation plan as well as the actual practical execution of the mid-scale test.

3.1. Methods/approach

Interview participants were pre-selected in the Description of Action, mainly based on demonstrated interest in the topic. Some candidate interviewees appeared to be less suitable as

interview participants, either because they were not a data holder themselves or because they had already participated in the small-scale test of WP2. As a replacement two data holders were added, i.e. the Dutch Cancer Registry (IKNL) and Toulouse University Hospital.

A standardised interview guide was created (see Annex 1) which was sent to the participants prior to the interview. They were requested to return the interview guide with the information that they could already provide before the interview. The interview itself could then focus on the real discussion items. The results of the interview were subsequently entered in the interview guide which was reviewed and approved by the participants before finalized. Each of these interview guides is available on the WP3 Google Drive⁵ for further consideration when planning the mid-scale test.

3.2. Key outcomes of the interviews

Each of the completed and approved interview guides is available on the WP3 Google Drive providing all details for each of the data holders interviewed. There were distinct differences between the organisations in terms of experience with quality labels and their expectations. However, there were also quite some commonalities which are summarized in these high-level observations:

- **High-end data holders.** Most participants represented highly experienced and advanced data holders which have a high-level of awareness and professionalism with respect to data quality.
 - **Recommendation:** when recruiting participants for the mid-scale test we should ensure that also less experienced and structured data holders will be included to ensure the representativeness of the test.
- **No pre-existing quality labels.** While all interviewees have data quality processes in place and most of them were actively working on improving those, none of them had distinct quality or utility labels in use. If any quality information was available to potential data users, it was usually hidden in free-text metadata.
- **Automation expected.** Several interviewees were expecting a fully or at least partially automated tool that would extract the quality labels from the datasets without human intervention. It was for some of them a disappointment that the data labels have to be entered manually.
 - **Recommendation:** it should be clearly communicated to the test participants that the tool requires manual data entry.
- **Concern for sensitive data.** Some of the interviewees were concerned for sensitive data leakage, which first of all resulted in (unnecessary) reluctance to use the online tool. For the on-premise tool the concern was raised whether the metadata or the RDF file would be sent over to the central tool.
 - **Recommendation:** it should be clearly communicated that participating in the test does not yield any sensitive data issues.
- **High expectations.** All interviewees were very keen to participate in the test and have very high expectations of the QUANTUM quality labeling tool. This may lead to major disappointment when issues are encountered as can be expected in a mid-scale test.

⁵ [Link to QUANTUM google drive with interview guides](#)

- **Recommendation:** The expectations should be very clearly set when recruiting test participants. They should also be encouraged to speak up and highlight any issues encountered during the test.
- **Local vs on-line tool usage.** There was a nice variety of preferences with respect to the actual implementation of the tool: some organisations are planning to use the on-line tool, some to install locally, and again some others intend to test both. There does not appear to be a need to actively steer users towards one or the other.

Some of these interview outcomes have also been added to the risk and mitigation table at the end of this implementation plan.

4. Execution of the mid-scale test

4.1. Tool installation

Within QUANTUM the labeling tool will be made available for local stand-alone installation and remotely via a QUANTUM hosted web application. Both versions of the tool will basically have the same user-interface. The local stand-alone installation will be a Docker container image (more info on Docker container images see: <https://www.docker.com/resources/what-container/>). Test participants are free to use either of the installation options or even both of them. The interviews performed in task 3.1 showed that there is adequate diversity in the preference of the users ensuring both installation options are sufficiently tested. There is no need to actively manage which option the participants will use. The interviews also showed that the participants appear to be aware of potential technical hurdles and certainly the ones that have elected to use both versions have access to local technical support to assist in installing the dockerized tool. How that will materialize in practice is of course part of the actual test and one of the important outcomes.

4.2. Installation support & helpdesk

Based on the interviews two major types of support are identified: 1) Support at the technical deployment level of the tool for those cases where testers will use the locally implemented QUANTUM tool, and 2) general user support related to the usability of the tool.

Important aspects to evaluate during the mid-scale test are the ease of the local stand-alone installation and the usability of the tool. For both aspects it would be required that the tool is self-explanatory to a great extent. The test participants will therefore be provided only with concise and clear documentation for 1) the installation and the use of the tool itself and 2) the information required to back the assessment. This high-level documentation will link to more detailed information for further reading.

A realistic test setting requires that the support for the test users participating in the mid-scale test is not too intense initially such that any bias in evaluation of ease of installation and use of the tool is minimised.

The pilot users interviewed for this implementation plan consistently indicated they would expect

active support in case problems are met or questions pop up during the mid-scale test. The interviewees also indicated that support through ad hoc on-line meetings (MS Teams, Zoom or similar tooling) would be expected in case of more complicated matters. For this reason, task 3.2 will implement a specific help desk that can be reached by phone, email (helpdesk@quantumproject.eu) and a ticketing tool, and will document all relevant problems and questions raised and answers provided. This documentation will help to determine if any bias in the evaluation might be present due to support provided.

Questions and issues raised at the helpdesk will be used to populate an on-line repository of frequently asked questions (FAQ) that can be consulted by future testers.

4.3. Selection of test participants

A predefined list of test participants is already available from the QUANTUM proposal. Also all participants in the task 3.1 interview series indicated that they are willing to join the midscale test (as expected). These data holders also indicated the dataset(s) they are intending to use as the test case in this mid-scale test. The overview of these committed participants can be found in Annex 2.

The scheduling of the testers over the various test rounds will be done in more detail at the start of each test round, first of all based on the preferences and availability of the data holders involved, but an adequate coverage of the various dataset and data holder properties will be taken into account, namely:

- Anticipated maturity of the data holder
- Data type of the dataset (tabular versus non-tabular data; clinical trial data, statistical data, health data, imaging data, genomics data etc.)
- Size of the dataset: e.g. full data registry vs. small research study
- Geographic coverage across European member states
- Etc.

The actual selection of data holders to participate in each test run will be done on the basis of a survey that will be sent out to all potential participants at the start of the mid-scale test (April 2025). See below in Section 4.5.2 for more details.

4.4. Capturing the test results

The results of the mid-scale test will be captured in two steps: 1) through an online form gathering the findings in a structured manner and guiding the testers to consider all aspects needed, and 2) in an online recap meeting to be organised 1-on-1 with each of the data holders participating in the mid-scale test. These meetings will be used to get clarity on issues highlighted by the testers which require more explanation, and to discuss the more generic suggestions for improvement which may be hard to distill from an online form only.

The online form design and interviews will be conducted in conjunction with Task 3.3. This will make it easier to gather all the comments and suggestions from the pilot developers in a single step, while reducing their workload.

4.4.1. On-line test survey

The test survey to be used in the mid-scale test will be shared with the test participants before the test in Word format allowing them to discuss the test results among themselves before filling out the on-line survey. The form to be used will be based on the format previously used in WP2 (for the small-scale test) but is still to be further fine-tuned. At least one person per testing organisation, with oversight of the label and the organisation, will be interviewed. The current draft can be found in Annex 3.

The high-level topics to be considered by the test participants are:

- **Usability** of the tool's user interface: Is the tool's navigation logical and clear? Is the tool usage self-explanatory and if documentation/explanation is needed is it readily available through e.g. tool tips or explaining text?
- **Workflow** aspects: Is the workflow offered by the tool logical and user friendly, e.g. in the way mandatory fields are presented and handled? Will it easily allow you to save sessions and resume? And can the outputs easily be used in local metadata schemes and tooling?
- **Evaluation of the quality labels**: Are the QUANTUM quality and utility dimensions and the translation into corresponding labels clear, and can they readily be applied on the test dataset?
- **Effort** required: What was the effort required to provide the quality labels in the tool? Was this effort reasonable and how can we improve the efficiency of the tool usage to reduce the effort in the future?
- **Required skills**: What user profiles are best suited to carry out a health data quality assessment?
- **Transferability and sustainability**: What would key issues be to get the label transferables and sustainable over the years?

4.4.2. Test evaluation call

The test evaluation call will be scheduled shortly after the actual test but after the participating data holder has submitted the form with the evaluation results. It will be used to get clarity on any issues reported and have a discussion about possible improvements in the tool or the quality labels. Whether such an evaluation call will be needed may depend on the responses given by the test participant in the survey form. In some cases follow-up by email will suffice.

4.5. Planning of the mid-scale test

4.5.1. Kick-off meeting

The actual execution of the mid-scale test will be kicked-off with a joint (online) meeting with all potential test users identified, highlighting the fundamentals of the QUANTUM quality & utility labels, the tool to be tested and the practicalities of the execution of the mid-scale test. Amongst the practicalities to discuss during the kick of meeting, providing the participants with a clear idea of the scope and the methodology of this mid-scale implementation, what would the expected effort be, what the communication flows (ticketing system) and any further involvement in the

implementation assessment reacting to the final WP3.1 deliverables.

All contact persons listed in Annex 2 will be invited for this kick-off meeting which is now tentatively scheduled for April 15th.

4.5.2. Pre-test survey of potential participants

During the first phase of the pilot (Apr 2025), an online form will be made available to all potential participants, to collect a clean pilot census. In this form, potential participants will provide information about:

- the data-holder institution and type of institution (data hub, big or small hospital, academia, etc)
- contacts in the institution regarding the pilot, and users to be authorized in the online tool
- what is the role that they usually play in the institution
- anticipated maturity of the institution / department: high experience in data management and quality assessment, low or no experience, with or without IT department support
- their intended participation (first round, second round, other, indifferent)
- the dataset(s) to be assessed:
 - a single dataset or several datasets
 - tabular datasets, image, genomic, free text, others
- tool to be used:
 - online
 - on-premise (Docker)
 - both

4.5.3. Anticipated test cycles

Two main rounds of testing are anticipated. After the first round of testing the collective results will be discussed with WP2, which will lead to an updated version of the tool in which the issues highlighted in the first round of testing will have been fixed as fully as possible. Before releasing this updated version of the tool for the next/second test round to the test community the T3.2 team will execute an in-house acceptance test of the updated version of the tool to ensure we release a clean version to our test users. Towards the end of the mid-scale test we scheduled a small-scale third round of testing that is meant to fill any gaps in our test coverage (in terms of data holders, data types, etc.) that have been identified in the meantime.

4.5.4. High-level planning

The summary of the planning of the mid-scale test can be found in the Gantt chart below:

	Apr 25	May 25	Jun 25	Jul 25	Aug 25	Sep 25	Oct 25	Nov 25	Dec 25
Approach first-round testers; agree on dataset									
Kick-off meeting mid-scale test	April 15 th								
Run test (first round)									
Collect feedback & evaluation calls (in conjunction with T3.3)									
Align with WP2 on test findings									
Contact second- round testers; agree on dataset									
Acceptance of new tool version									
Run test (second round)									
Collect feedback & evaluation calls (in conjunction with T3.3)									
Contact selected third-round testers (“gap filling test”)									
Run test (third round)									
Collect results from gap test (in conjunction with T3.3)									
Closure & evaluation of mid-scale test									

4.5.5. Coordinated communication towards test participants

The responsibility for communication between QUANTUM and the participants in the mid-scale pilot lies with the coordinators of task 3.2, namely IACS and HDH.

All the institutions listed in the annex 2 of this document will be contacted through the contact emails indicated, to invite them to the kick-off meeting of task 3.2. Additionally, the invitation will be sent to the WP3 mail list (wp3@quantumproject.eu), so all the contributors of the work package 3 will be informed of the start of the mid-scale pilot activities.

After the kick-off meeting, an online form will be available for all of them, to gather specific

information about the institutions and persons involved in the development of the pilot, and the communication from the coordination will be mainly addressed to those registered in the pilot census (see section 4.5.2). The communication will be done individually, when needed, or collectively, to inform about relevant issues, like the release of an updated version of the tool.

The bidirectional communication between each participant and the project coordination will be done preferably through the ticketing tool. This way, it will be possible to keep track of the questions raised, forward them to the most appropriate person, and maintain a history of all questions and responses.

All the packages and tasks involved directly or indirectly in the pilot (particularly WP1, WP2, T3.2 and T3.3) will have access and resolver role in the ticketing system. The responsibility of setting up and managing the ticketing system will correspond to the task 3.2 coordination.

4.6. Collection & reporting of issues found

To facilitate the reporting of incidents, questions, and problems by pilot participants, a **ticketing tool** will be set up where users can open queries and service requests. Queries may relate to:

- the development and execution of the pilot (i.e., implementation barriers and facilitators)
- issues regarding concepts (definitions, metrics, information required) related to data quality or organizational maturity
- problems in the use of the tool or when installing the Docker version on-premise

Queries opened in the tool will be forwarded to different problem solvers, depending on the nature of the query. Participants of the different packages (WP1, WP2, T3.2, and T3.3) will have access to the tool to respond to and resolve the queries submitted to them.

Users participating in the pilot will be able to receive responses and track their queries through the ticketing tool.

Recurring queries or those of particular interest will be included in the FAQ section of the QUANTUM online tagging tool. All this information will also be available to T3.3 in order to obtain detailed and timely information from the users about the aspects they must report.

For the convenience of the users involved in the pilot, an email (helpdesk@quantumproject.eu) has been set up to allow direct and quick communication with T3.2. In case of limiting problems for the users to go on with the pilot, an online meeting will be scheduled between T3.2 and the user to unblock and resolve any obstacle.

Regular meetings will be held between the different work packages involved after each phase of the pilot in order to discuss the issues found, detect any bias, and make any change on the next phase plan.

4.7 Capacity building

The pilot will be a source of potential content for the capacity building programme developed in

the WP4. All those questions collected via the ticketing system deemed to be valuable content for the QUANTUM Academy, will be transferred to the WP4 leads for eventual use as part of the syllabus.

5. Summary of mid-scale test findings

Interviews with participating organisations will be conducted after testing to collect information about the implementation experiences, covering the areas of:

- feasibility of fully implementing the tool;
- acceptance of the quality, utility and maturity specifications and labelling tool;
- institutional preparedness;
- governance of the implementation;
- support for the implementation;
- barriers and facilitators;
- required resources and opportunity costs;
- transferability and sustainability of this labelling mechanism, in particular related to the interoperability of the label with existing data quality management procedures and dataset publication.

To be able to discuss the organisational aspects it is crucial to identify interviewees in each organisation who have an oversight of the label and the organisation.

Focus group(s) will be scheduled with those involved in the testing of the label. The aim of the focus group(s) is to explore areas covered above in more detail, to stimulate open, interactive discussions and to bring together people from across countries and organisations. This will facilitate greater breadth and depth of findings. The number of focus groups will be determined depending on the number of interviews held, limiting each group to a manageable size. Also the required diversity of the participants has to be considered: data quality managers, people with governance oversight of the organisation / data quality structures, and those involved in hands-on testing of the label. These could be the same or different persons, depending on the organisation.

Together with the results generated as described in the sections above, this will be analysed and composed into a report (deliverable D3.1) which aims at gathering the learnings from the mid-scale tests, covering all aforementioned aspects in a structured way. This report should serve as a resource for further improvement of the quality, utility and maturity specification, as well as for the tool implementing the specification. Furthermore, it will serve as input for the guidelines and recommendations directed towards the future implementation of the quality and utility label in the context of EHDS (deliverable D3.2).

6. Risk analysis & contingency plan

A number of potential risks have been identified from the interviews held in task 3.1 and from the general discussions in the WP3 project team. The main ones with their contingencies and mitigation measures are listed in the table below.

Risk	Contingency/mitigation
Test participants will be reluctant to share their true opinion on the tool and the quality label	Provide clear instructions and create a feedback form that is easy to use; organise interview sessions to get more in-depth feedback
Test participants will be reluctant to participate out of fear to disclose sensitive or personal data	Clearly communicate that the tool will not use or leak personal data.
Test participant may expect a high-level of automation and may be disappointed that manual data entry is required	Clearly set expectations at the mid-scale test kick-off and in the outreach to the test users.
Many more candidate test participants expect to join the mid-scale test than we can handle logistically resulting in disappointed partners	Create an early assessment of the capacity to participate and clearly communicate who can participate and when this will be decided
WP2 is not able to timely address the issues found in the first round of testing resulting in a delay of the second and third round of testing	Start planning bug fixing early on; front-load WP2 with issues found to arrive at a more fluid test-report-fix cycle.
Unclear how an HDAB will be able to withdraw a label.	A potential solution will be to keep/store the quality labels separately from the metadata record as provided by the dataholder as is currently implemented with the QUANTUM tool. Otherwise the dataholder will be able to update that record any time and if the quality label is part of that record will overwrite the withdrawn label by HDAB. This requires being able to link the quality related metadata of dataset X with the metadata record of the same dataset X.
Tool not compliant with EU interoperability test bed	Implementing a specific action in WP2 to get compliance

Annex 1 – Interview Guide used for the task 3.1 interviews

In-depth interviews with Implementers of the QUANTUM labelling tool in advance of the mid-scale pilot

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Proposed method of taking the interviews:

- send this list of questions to the person(s) to interview and ask them to prepare themselves so the interview can be finished once held. Ideally if possible the interview questions can be pre-filled and send to us to together be optimally prepared for the interview

Contact details of person(s) to interview:

Your full name:

Organization name:

Your (professional) role within your organisation:

Your email:

Optional your Tel:

1. Objectives of the in-depth interview

This in-depth interview will be done with the implementers/users of the QUANTUM tool to establish quality labels for datasets. The interviews will be held in advance of the planned implementation and testing (within QUANTUM called the mid-scale pilot) of the tool. The targeted interviewees will be data holders (as defined in the EHDS). The actual pilot is scheduled to take place in a number of testing rounds from April 2025 till December 2025.

With this in-depth interview we would like to get an overview of:

- your institutional preparedness for the implementation of the QUANTUM labeling tool
- potential barriers in using the tool, e.g. whether you will be able to implement automatic procedures for the assessment or have to rely on manual approaches
- risk analysis and contingency plan for the deployment of the tool
- your expectations with respect to the testing and the QUANTUM labeling tool

The results of this interview will help us (better) preparing for the implementation as well as for the actual implementation of the QUANTUM tool.

For the interviews we use the following concepts as used within the QUANTUM project:

Quality refers to features that describe the content of a dataset, typically completeness, uniqueness, accuracy, validity, timeliness, and consistency of the data.

Fit-for-use is equivalent to a dataset's "potential" utility, typically information that describes the dataset in a standard manner, such as source, provenance or lineage, content, distribution, etc. Fit-for-use talks about the "potential" utility of a dataset, while the actual utility can only be informed by the user experience—in QUANTUM, the actual utility is referred to as fit-for-purpose.

Fit-for-purpose refers to the actual utility of an accessed dataset according to the objective of the data request. The information necessary to evaluate fit-for-purpose depends on the user's experience. This information needs to be added to the description of a dataset as a fit-for-purpose meta-data.

Maturity is a feature at the data holder level. It refers to the level of automation of data and data quality management procedures.

Below is a list of the topics and questions for the in-dept interviews:

Existing procedure(s)/workflow(s) on data quality and/or data utility:

- Could you walk us through the specific procedures or workflows you currently use to document and/or ensure data quality? Please include any steps or strategies that are part of these processes and describe, if possible, if it is a manual, semi-automated, or fully

automated step.

- Could you describe the specific procedures or workflows you have in place to document and/or ensure data utility? Please detail the steps and strategies involved in these processes and describe, if possible, if it is a manual, semi-automated, or fully automated step.
- Could you indicate whether you have documentation (of parts of) the current procedure or not?
 - if yes, and you are able to share them with us please (upload/mail) them
- If a dataset is produced according to the current procedures how is the data quality and/or data utility expressed, made known, made available and/or made findable?
- Which role or function within your organization is responsible for determining the data quality (label)? Can you describe the responsibilities and tasks associated with the role that oversees data quality?
- Which role or function within your organization is responsible for determining the data utility (label)? Can you describe the responsibilities and tasks associated with the role that oversees data utility?

Starting point regarding data quality management maturity:

- Could you walk us through the specific procedures or workflows you currently use to document and/or ensure the maturity of your data quality management? Please include any steps or strategies that are part of these processes.

As example to get inspiration we have include various data maturity aspects for data holders in the matrix below:

Serial	Dimension	Definition	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5	Reference	Comments
1	Data collection process	The processes relating to the capture of data from multiple sources for secondary purposes	Initial: a new or undocumented process, unpredictable, poorly controlled and reactive	Ad hoc processes exist for data collection	Defined: the process is defined and confirmed as a standard process	Managed: the process is quantitatively and proactively managed in accordance with agreed-upon metrics	Optimised: process management includes deliberate process optimisation	ISO 8000-62 data maturity model	
2	Data management - governance	The level of maturity of the data management processes	No data collection or capture process for secondary purposes	Ad hoc processes exist for data collection	Defined processes exist for some data collection	Defined processes exist for all data collection and are used for secondary purposes	Processes are automated for all data collection, focus on continuous process improvement	Adapted HDRLUK	Covers more than just data management planning
3	Data management - infrastructure	The level of implementation and development of the data holder's data management infrastructure	No documented data management governance	A documented data management (post covering) collection, auditing and management is available for the dataset	Evidence that the data management plan has been implemented is available	Demonstrated compliance with the data management plan	Externally verified compliance with the data management plan	European Health Data Space / FAIR	Cover security of infrastructure (throughout the dimensions)
4	Data provenance	Clear description of source and history of the dataset, providing a "transparent data pipeline"	No data management infrastructure	An emerging data management infrastructure, some validation and verification	Data management infrastructure defined and confirmed as a standard process	Data management infrastructure, with partially automated, verified and validated (real time) data management	Ability to view earlier versions, including "raw" or "source" dataset, and review the impact of each step/step	Adapted HDRLUK	
5	Data access	How well defined and implemented are data access processes, from a legal, ethical and technical perspective	No data access processes or procedures	Source of the dataset is documented	Source of the dataset and any transformations, rules and exclusions	All original data items listed, all transformations, rules and exclusion listed and impact of these	Ability to view earlier versions, including "raw" or "source" dataset, and review the impact of each step/step	European Health Data Space / FAIR	Cross reference to EHDS Trusted Data Holder
6	Data analytics environment	Analytical services, tooling and access to (existing) data environments	No data access processes or procedures	Have the processes and procedures, and respond in timely and consistent manner	Have the processes and procedures, and respond in timely and consistent manner	Data access system that covers both technical and policy areas, in accordance with agreed metrics	A comprehensive data access system that covers technical, ethical and policy areas (allowable uses, API documentation, access and approvals) compliant with EU Policy	Adapted HDRLUK	
7	Data enhancement - augmentation	The application of various techniques to make data more usable for specific purposes	No data environment available	Requested analysis can be undertaken by internal teams and provided back in anonymised format to data requestors	The dataset can be used in a secure data environment (SDE)	The dataset can be used in an SDE and other data and tools can be brought in as required	The dataset can be used in federated or organised environment	OMOP / OpenEHR / HL7 FHIR / ISO/IEC 29500-21/22	This is different from Data enrichment. They are both subtypes of Data Enhancement.
8	Data enhancement - enrichment	Data sources enriched for example with annotations, image labels, phenoms, derivations, NLP derived data labels	No data augmentation	Some techniques to make data more useable for specific purposes	Defined techniques to make data more useable for specific purposes	Managed techniques to make data more useable for specific purposes	Comprehensive application of various techniques and mapping to data model (i.e. OMOP to make more useable for specific purposes)	Adapted HDRLUK	This is different from Data augmentation. They are both subtypes of Data Enhancement.
9	Data Model	Availability of clear, documented data model that provides structure and standardisation	The data has no additional derived fields, or enriched data.	The data include additional derived fields, or enriched data.	The data include additional derived fields, or enriched data used by other available data sources.	The derived fields or enriched data were generated from, or used by, a peer reviewed algorithm.	The data includes derived fields or enriched data from an internal national report	Adapted HDRLUK / OMOP / OpenEHR / HL7 FHIR	Interoperability and Standardisation
10	Data Dictionary	Provided documented data dictionary and terminologies	There is no data model	Known and accepted data model but some key field uncoded or free text	Key fields codified using a local standard and updated over time	Key fields codified using a national or international standard and updated over time	Local report common to an (inter) national standard and key fields codified using a national / international standard and updated over time	Adapted HDRLUK / FAIR	Link to Metadata Standards and Definitions

- If data maturity is assessed/available could you please indicate:
 - At what level data maturity assessment is carried out (e.g. at dataset level, at departmental/unit level, or at organisation level)?
 - Which role or function within your organization is responsible for determining the data maturity? Can you describe the responsibilities and tasks associated with the role that oversees data maturity?
 - Could you indicate whether you have documentation (of parts of) the current procedure or not?
 - if yes, and you are able to share them with us please (upload/mail) them

Preference for type of implementation of tool:

Within QUANTUM the labeling tool will be made available for local stand-alone installation and

remotely via a QUANTUM hosted web application. Both versions of the tool will basically have the same user-interface.

The local stand-alone installation will be a Docker container image (more info on Docker container images see: <https://www.docker.com/resources/what-container/>)

- Please select the option for implementing the QUANTUM labeling tool that would be possible for you:
 - local stand-alone implementation
 - remotely hosted web application
 - both local stand-alone implementation and remotely hosted web application are possible but we only will be implementing one
 - both local stand-alone implementation and remotely hosted web application are possible and we will implement both
- Please describe why you prefer the selected type of implementation?

Expectations and Objectives for the implementation of the QUANTUM labeling tool:

- **Local stand-alone type of implementation:**

You have selected that you will implement the local stand-alone QUANTUM labeling tool provided as a Docker container image. We would like you to answer the following detailed and specific questions to better understand the requirements and environment of you or your organization implementing the Docker container image. Below we use the term “target machine” which refers to the computer/system where the Docker container image will be deployed and used.

Environment Setup:

- Is the target machine a personal computer, the infrastructure of your institute, or a cloud-hosted environment?
- What operating system and version are you using on the target machine?
- Do you have Docker installed on the target machine? If so, which version of Docker are you currently using?

System Requirements:

- Can you confirm the system specifications (CPU, RAM, storage) of the target machine?
- Do you have any network restrictions or firewall settings that we need to be aware of for downloading the Docker image or communicating with external services?

Permissions and Access:

- Do you have the necessary administrative permissions to install and run Docker containers on the target machine? If not, who does?
- Do you have access to the Docker Hub or a private Docker registry to pull the container image?
- Are there any specific security policies or restrictions we should consider during installation? If so please describe them.
- Are there any specific data privacy or compliance requirements that need to be addressed? If so please describe them.

- **Remotely web based application type of implementation:**

You have selected that you will implement the remotely QUANTUM hosted web application. We would like you to answer the following questions to better understand the requirements and environment of you or your organization implementing/using the QUANTUM hosted web

application.

Environment Setup:

- Which (internet)browsers do you or your users typically use? Are there any specific compatibility requirements we should be aware of?
- Are there any specific security policies or restrictions we should consider that might influence use/testing of the QUANTUM web application? If so please describe them. (e.g. no javascript allowed; no downloads allowed from browser to local harddrives if working at home)
- Are there any specific data privacy or compliance requirements that need to be addressed? If so please describe them.

- **Key factors for successful implementation and expected support**
- What kind of support or resources (e.g. documentation, a service/helpdesk, specific feedback mechanisms) would you need from our side to ensure a smooth implementation?
- Is there a preferred method of communication for support if you encounter any issues? If yes, please specify.

- **Which dataset(s) will be used for the mid-scale test?**
 - For each dataset you will use during one or more tests please provide answers on the questions below:
 - Type of dataset (e.g. imaging data, biomarker data, electronic health records, clinical trial data, genomic/ transcriptomic/ metabolomic/ proteomic data, population data, public health data, social determinants of health data, financial/claims data, wearable device data)
 - Description of dataset
 - Who is the data controller of this dataset?
 - Describe if the dataset as well as corresponding (quality) documentation can be used, are available, during testing?

- **How many test rounds will be done?**
 - How many times are you willing to test (and potentially implement) a new version of the tool given the feedback that we will obtain from your testing? Please select one of the options below:
 - only once with initial version
 - only once with final version
 - multiple released versions (we expect 2 or 3 versions) with same datasets
 - multiple released versions (we expect 2 or 3 versions) each time with different datasets
 - other, please specify

General insights:

- What other barriers and challenges to implementation, or expectations do you foresee regarding implementing the QUANTUM labelling tool?

- What are the benefits you foresee by implementing and using the QUANTUM labelling tool?
- Do you have any specific expectations for the QUANTUM labeling tool you would like to share?

Annex 2 - Overview of anticipated mid-scale test participants

Data holder	Contact person(s)	Datatype	Dataset description	Comments
Sciensano (BE)	Claudio.ProiettiMercuri@sciensano.be ; pierre.hubin@sciensano.be	Registry health data	TP_VACC19 (pseudonymized vaccination data). Registry data extracted from health records	They plan to use the remote tool
French Data Hub (FR)	amelie.schafer@health-data-hub.fr	n/a	n/a	Acting like an HDAB, is the coordinating entity of French hospitals participating in the project, namely Lyon, Bordeaux and Toulouse
CHU Toulouse (FR)	jouffrey.t@chu-toulouse.fr feuille.t@chu-toulouse.fr	Derived data from electronic health records	To be determined: could be a previously released (real world example) dataset in OMOP-like format or we create one on the fly of the clinical data from our EHR-system in OMOP-like format.	One of the hospitals from the French HDH network. Contact Persons: Tania Jouffrey and Laure Feuillet. They will start with the on-site installation, and may be interested to test the web version in the second round.
CHU de Bordeaux (FR)	vianney.jouhet@chu-bordeaux.fr	tbd	tbd	Have already participated in the WP2 small-scale pilot but may participate in the WP3 mid-scale pilot with another database
Hospices Civils de Lyon (FR)	francois.talbot@chu-lyon.fr . marie.viprey@chu-lyon.fr delphine.maucort-boulch@chu-lyon.fr	tbd	tbd	Will participate in the mid-scale pilot starting in April (are funded accordingly)

	lyon.fr			
APHM (FR)	Laurent.BOYER@ap-hm.fr philippe.leca@ap-hm.fr pascal.auquier@univ-amu.fr, francois.cremieux@ap-hm.fr,	tbd	tbd	Sub-contractor of the Health Data Hub and will participate in the mid-scale pilot starting in April (are funded accordingly)
CHRU Lille (FR)	Charlotte.FERRAN@chu-lille.fr	tbd	tbd	Sub-contractor of the Health Data Hub and will participate in the mid-scale pilot starting in April (are funded accordingly)
CHU de Montpellier (FR)	c-dunoyer@chu-montpellier.fr	tbd	tbd	Sub-contractor of the Health Data Hub and will maybe (tbd) participate in the mid-scale pilot starting in April
BBMRI ERIC (AT)	eva.garcia-alvarez@bbmri-eric.eu ; niina.eklund@bbmri-eric.eu	Clinical data, imaging, genomics data	Collection of more than 10,000 European cases of colorectal cancer, collected as a part of the ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC project. It contains structured and curated clinical data. In addition, scans of histopathological slides and genomic data are available for a subset of cases.	They will use the local standalone version
THL (FI)	oon.pentala-nikulainen@thl.fi annaleena.okuloff@thl.fi gustav.klingstedt@thl.fi mari.makinen@thl.fi	National health care registry data	Finnish Care Register for Health Care (Terveys-Hilmo)	Want to use the web version of the tool
NIJZ (SI)	Metka.Zaletel@nijz.si ; Tina.Zupanic@nijz.si	Tbd (data holder of statistical population data)	Tbd	Probably first the web version will be used, but also interest in testing the local version at a later stage

NIPHM (NO)	Truls.Korsgaard@fhi.no Anne.heidi.skogholt@helsedir.no	Two parties involved: Cancer Registry Norway and Norwegian HDAB	Datasets are still to be determined from: Cancer Registry of Norway (CRN): Data products + OMOP-version of core CRN-variables ECIS data protocol Norwegian HDAB: Cancer Registry of Norway Norwegian Cause of Death Registry	Other people involved: Hans Aage Huru. Siri Larønningen, Gintaras Pikelis. (Hans.aage.huru@fhi.no Sla@kreftregisteret.no) They would like to test both the standalone and the online version
IKNL (NL)	m.sloep@iknl.nl	Cancer registry	The Dutch Cancer Registry (general and breast tumour set, Population based cancer registry data)	Dutch Cancer Center brought in by Health-RI. Contact person Matthijs Sloep. Other people involved: Peter Prinsen, Relinde Uppelschoten, Gijs Geleijnse p.prinsen@iknl.nl r.uppelschoten@iknl.nl g.geleijnse@iknl.nl They are willing to test both the standalone and the online version.
EUHA (BE/international)	m.garriga@euhalliance.eu johan.vaneldere@euhalliance.eu	Pre-cleaned medical data	Breast cancer data derived from medical records	EUHA represents a network of academic medical centers and maintain a common breast cancer data set; contact person: Martina Garriga. Possible participants from their network: Charité, UZ Leuven, Vall d'Hebron, Erasmus MC, and AKH-MedUni Wien
Optional participants contacted from T3.1 not having participated in the interviews of T3.1				

SPMS (PT)	nuno.cruz.ext@spms.min-saude.pt			No bandwidth to participate in interviews but WP3 participant
CHU Bordeaux (FR)	vianney.jouhet@chu-bordeaux.fr			One of the hospitals from the French HDH network; already participated in the small-scale test
GOG (AT)	lorenz.dolanski@goeg.at			Not a dataholder but able to reach out to data holders in the network
iHD (BE/international)	jens.declerck@i-hd.eu			Not a dataholder but able to reach out to data holders in the network
Additional participants listed in the DoA for T3.2				
VIB (BE)	frederik.coppens@vib.be ; dilza.campos@vib.be			
CIPH (HR)	emanuel.bradasevic@hzjz.hr moris.bagic@hzjz.hr ivan.pristas@hzjz.hr jakov.vukovic@hzjz.hr			National HDAB and data holder
HUS (FI)	pekka.kahri@hus.fi matias.tolppanen@hus.fi			
ECRIN (FR/international)	maria.rujano@ecrin.org			
ISS (IT)	giuseppe.davenio@iss.it carla.daniele@iss.it			

	mariarosaria.napolitano@iss.it annalisa.abballe@iss.it			
CESSDA ERIC (NO/international)	alen.vodopijavec@cessda.eu cecile.guezennec@cessda.eu panagiota.starida@cessda.eu			
KNAW/DANS (NL)	Wim Hugo < wim.hugo@dans.knaw.nl > kim.ferguson@dans.knaw.nl cees.hof@dans.knaw.nl			
UESSEX (UK)	dbell@essex.ac.uk oparke@essex.ac.uk			
EHELSE (NO)	anne.heidi.skogholt@helsedir.no truls.korsgaard@fhi.no inge.voldseth@fhi.no			
UPORTO (PT)	alberto@med.up.pt			
ErasmusMC (NL)	m.moinat@erasmusmc.nl p.rijnbeek@erasmusmc.nl			
Additional candidate testers that have contacted us at a later stage				
KU Leuven (BE)	ahmed.zayed@kuleuven.be	Registry of first-line care data	Intego.be	Interest raised though Sciensano (Claudio Proietti Mercuri)

CBS (NL)	i.gorissen@cbs.nl	National Bureau of Statistics	Population health data	Very large data holder; partner in Dutch HDAB project; expressed their interest to participate.
RIVM (NL)	coen.van.gool@rivm.nl	National institute for population health	Population health data, vaccination data	Very large data holder; partner in Dutch HDAB project; responsible for Dutch implementation of quality label
EUCAIM (ES/international)	iblanque@dsic.upv.es	Future EDIC	Cancer imaging data	Have contacted Enrique that they would like to participate

Annex 3 - survey questions to be presented to test participants

- Institution / Organization/Role
- Dataset(s) assessed
- Version / Modality of the tool
- Evaluation of the pilot
 - Time to execute a complete assessment of a dataset
 - Held desk operation
 - Problems understanding elements or steps in the pilot
 - Maturity assessment, useful to focus on how to improve the maturity of your organization
- Evaluation of the tool
 - Operation of the tool. Errors or malfunction
 - Usability of the tool (in general)
 - Management of catalogues and datasets
 - Easy / Difficult to understand concepts
 - Useful apart from labeling datasets
 - Easy to manage
 - Assessment of a dataset
 - type of dataset
 - Generation and visualization of the label and certificate (RDF, PDF)
 - Easy to generate
 - Benefits and disadvantages
- Evaluation of the conceptualization of quality, utility and maturity dimensions
 - Quality dimensions
 - Utility dimensions
 - Maturity dimensions, maturity matrix
 - Generation and visualization of the label
 - Easy to understand the meaning of the label
 - Easy to understand de PDF report
- General comments/questions/insights not addressed